

Traditional Livestock Practices and Sustainability of old Growth Forests

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The link between traditional livestock practices and forest sustainability in Greece is characterized by significant synergies and conflicts, depending on how these practices are implemented. In general, grazing in forests has a positive impact on forests when it is regulated and does not reach the limits of overgrazing or does not include forest areas under regeneration. In remote and mountainous areas of Greece, such as *Evrytania*, traditional pastoral practices have been practised over time, including the maintenance of old-growth trees or stands. These were most often located at the boundaries of fields, in places where livestock were stabled or stayed and in places where, for religious, historical and traditional reasons, their protection was required (chapels, monuments, historical sites, etc.). These centuries-old trees were used in various ways by livestock farmers. They were pruned to provide food for the animals (foliage) and firewood for their individual needs. The large trees were also provided a resting place for cattle, especially in the summer months when shade was needed.

The result of this traditional communal form of management is nowadays the presence in the mountainous areas of *Evrytania*, in forest and agroforestry systems, of evergreen fir, holm, aria, deciduous oak, juniper or clusters of the previous species, which comprise habitats of high ecological value. Their presence today contributes to biodiversity and the fight against climate change, enhancing the features of the landscape and preserving the historical heritage and traditions of the area.

Unfortunately, the abandonment of the rural areas, the significant reduction in grazing and the lack of appropriate management are leading to the densification of the forests and the weakening and death of these monumental trees due to competition from the adjacent vegetation. Therefore, in the context of sustainable development and climate change mitigation, this traditional livestock farming practice, integrated today in the context of a sustainable grazing management of the forest pastures of *Evrytania*, can support the sustainability of perennial trees and forests as a legacy and heritage for future generations, to support activities related to livestock farming, agro-tourism, ecotourism and environmental education.

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